

Credit Vehicles and Urban Congestion: A Social Phenomenon

By El-Roi R M

In today's modern world, fast and flexible mobility is one of the main requirements for survival and excellence. Highways are not just a path for activities, but even though they are not racers, all drivers try to compete as fast as possible to reach their destinations for their respective purposes. In the midst of such tight and intense rush hours, congestion is the main obstacle that must be faced and passed by drivers, both motorbikes and cars. Squatting, looking for space and gaps, overtaking each other, inner conflict and can also be physical due to emotional turmoil between having to remain patient or having to be arrogant to oneself or to other drivers or road users are forms of social action that occur in the jungle called the highway.

Road users consist of motorcyclists and car drivers with various types of motorcycles and various types of cars with different functions, there are private vehicles, operational vehicles for agencies, private vehicles for work (motorcycle taxis, taxis), competing for speed and getting stuck in traffic jams due to the number of vehicles that are not comparable to the size of the road. The number of vehicles that increases significantly every year is not balanced with the road that does not increase.

The growth in the number of vehicles in Ambon City reaches an average of 10% per year. In 2021, the number of four-wheeled and six-wheeled vehicles operating in Ambon City reached 40,861 units, while two-wheeled vehicles reached 111,188 units, according to data from the Maluku Provincial Revenue Service. Meanwhile, based on data from the Electronic Registration and Identification (ERI) of the Indonesian National Police Traffic Corps in April 2025, the number of motorized vehicles in Ambon City reached 236,340 units, with motorcycles dominating at 205,720 units. This growth, when compared to data from 2021, shows a significant increase in the number of motorized vehicles in Ambon City.

More than two hundred and thirty thousand motorized vehicles (motorcycles and cars) pass on the city's highways, with the increasing number of vehicles and city roads that remain but do not increase, it will certainly cause congestion, which is increasingly seen and felt every day. The number of vehicles that exist is mostly dominated by private vehicles, this can be seen not only through data, it can also be seen directly with the naked eye, the majority of private vehicles, especially motorbikes fill the highway. The increasing volume of private vehicles that is not comparable to the road sections will certainly cause congestion.

This is what many other city governments have tried to overcome by enforcing regulations on using public transportation. Private vehicles (cars, motorbikes) take up more space per person than public transportation. Public transportation includes public transportation (angkot), buses, trains or fast trains. For the city of Ambon, the majority are public transportation or angkot.

However, the reality is, in the current condition of Ambon city, public transportation vehicles are actually decreasing in number, due to the large number of city residents who already

have private vehicles, especially motorbikes. Almost every family has one or two motorbikes, or one family has one car, or has two motorbikes and one car. Unlike in the past where private vehicles could only be owned by a few families, upper middle class families, in today's era, private vehicles, especially motorbikes, can be owned by almost every family class. Cars are still a luxury vehicle and cannot be freely accessed by all family classes. Motorbikes are now not only owned by the upper middle class but can also be owned by lower middle class families, with the exception perhaps for the extreme poor family class.

Motorcycles can be owned by various groups because it is easy to buy a motorcycle using a credit system. Motorized vehicles can not only be purchased in cash but can be purchased using a credit system that is paid with a low down payment of almost zero rupiah, with a long tenor and easy requirements using only a resident identity card (KTP), then pay monthly installments which if not paid then the motorcycle will be withdrawn by the motorcycle dealer. This makes segments of society that previously could not afford to buy a motorcycle in cash can now buy even more than one motorcycle in one family. This causes the number of motorcycles to increase much faster which results in many motorcycles multiplying and mushrooming on the roads, causing congestion.

Sociologically, the phenomenon of credit motorcycles when viewed through the perspective of rational choice theory, credit motorcycles offer low costs, fast mobility, high flexibility which are seen as the most rational choice by society. The decision of one or several people in a family to have their own personal motorcycles, if it is also done by their neighbors and other neighbors, then it will develop from an individual decision into a collective decision that causes a high number of motorcycles on the road. If many people make the same choice, an irrational condition is created collectively. Dysfunctional rational decisions result in widespread social losses in the form of congestion, pollution, and decreased quality of life in urban environments.

Viewed through the theory of structural functionalism, the ease of motorcycle credit which results in easy ownership, thus causing congestion, can be explained as an economic adaptation mechanism that allows people to meet their mobility needs. However, when this system is not balanced with the role of other systems, in this case road infrastructure, dysfunction will occur. Congestion is a form of social dysfunction in which elements of the social system (namely the credit system) which were initially functional to facilitate the purchase and ownership of vehicles change to be detrimental to the system by causing congestion.

In addition, in the theory of symbolic interactionism, owning a motorbike, even on credit, can provide a certain social status symbol. Having a private vehicle, in the eyes of most people, is considered a symbol of moving up a class for the working class and can be considered a symbol of success when compared to those who do not have private vehicles and take public transportation, let alone walking. Many people prefer to ride their own motorbike rather than public transportation because it is considered more "free", "independent", "cool", and "classy". This phenomenon shows that private motorbikes are not only a means of transportation but also a symbol of identity. When many people have this kind of symbolic mindset and act similarly due

to the influence of consumerism culture, there will be an explosion in the number of private vehicles that contribute to traffic jams.

The phenomenon of traffic jams as a result of easy motorcycle credit is not only a technical problem, but also a complex social dynamic. Therefore, the solution to the problem of traffic jams requires a multidimensional approach that includes improving the public transportation system, regulation of private vehicle ownership, use of private vehicle ownership on the highway, and changes in the culture of public consumption.